

This document presents the data collection instruments used in this project. The questionnaire is referred in the paper as (II) Online questionnaire for former inmates. It was made available online for a period of 9 months, from August 2021 to February 2022.

Seção 1 de 2

Assessment Questionnaire of the ESVirtual mobile application

Descrição do formulário

Informed Consent Form

You are being invited to participate in the research entitled "Evaluation of the Virtual Social Office mobile application," under the responsibility of the Brazilian National Council of Justice (CNJ) and researchers at the University of Brasília (UnB). This research aims to evaluate the quality of the Virtual Social Office mobile application (ESVirtual) through interviews, questionnaires, and usability evaluations, with former inmates of the Brazilian prison system to identify their perception of the application throughout their social reintegration process. You will receive all necessary explanations before, during, and after the research is completed, and we assure you that your name will not be disclosed and that the strictest confidentiality will be maintained by omitting any information that could identify you. The data resulting from your participation in the research, such as questionnaires, will be kept by the researchers responsible for the research.

Título

It is for these procedures that you are being invited to participate. Your participation in the survey carries minimal risks, such as any discomfort in answering a question. But no question is mandatory, so you can feel free not to answer anything that makes you uncomfortable. This survey is expected to identify aspects considered important by former inmates in their process of social reintegration and what services can be incorporated or improved within the ESVirtual. With this information, we intend to improve the information quality of the services available in the application. Your participation is voluntary and without remuneration or benefit. You are free to refuse to participate, withdraw your consent, or discontinue your participation at any time. If you have any questions regarding the research, you can contact the research team at QuestESV@gmail.com. The research team informs you that the study results will be returned through improvements in the application and they may be published later in the scientific community. As we will not collect any information identifying the participant, it will not be possible to provide results directly to individuals. This project was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee on Research in Human and Social Sciences (CEP/CHS) of the University of Brasília. Information regarding the ICF signature or the research participant's rights can be obtained through the CEP/CHS e-mail: cep_chs@unb.br or by phone: (+55 61 3107 1592).

CONSENT:

I believe that I have been sufficiently informed about the information that I have read or that has been read to me describing the study "Evaluation of the Virtual Social Office". It is clear to me what the purposes are, the procedures to be performed, their discomforts and risks, the guarantees of confidentiality, and ongoing clarification. It is also clear that my participation is free of charge. I voluntarily agree to participate in this study and may withdraw my consent at any time, before or during the study, without penalties or losses.

By selecting the option "Yes..." you indicate that you agree to answer the questions in this questionnaire.

- Yes. I have read and agree to participate in the research
- I do not agree to participate in the research

Após a seção 1 Enviar formulário

Seção 2 de 2

Título da seção (opcional)

Descrição (opcional)

What is your school degree?

- No formal education
- Primary School incomplete
- Primary School complete
- High School incomplete
- High School complete

- High school complete
- University Education incomplete
- University Education complete
- Post-graduation, Master's or PhD complete

Over how many years have you been using applications on your mobile phone?

Texto de resposta curta

Have you ever been to a physical Social Office?

- Yes
- No

If so, were your questions answered there?

- Yes
- No

Do you already use the Social Virtual Office (ESVirtual) mobile application? If so, for how long?

Texto de resposta curta

Did you use the app to search for something specific or just to get to know what it had to offer?

- Search for something
- Get to know what the application had to offer

If it was to search for something in the app, could you tell us what?

Texto de resposta longa

Have you been able to obtain access to any service or right after obtaining information from the application? If yes, could you tell us which one?

Texto de resposta longa

What did you like the most about the application?

Texto de resposta longa

What did you find most difficult in using the application?

Texto de resposta longa

What is your opinion about the following statements? (Select one option per line)

	Completely dis...	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Completely agr...
Initiatives like t...	☐				
The application...	☐				
The application...	☐				
The application...	☐				
The application...	☐				

How would you rate your satisfaction with the application's usage?

- Unsatisfied
- Neutral
- Satisfied

How do you evaluate the information offered by the application as useful in your social reintegration process? (Select one option per line)

	Useless	Not very useful	Neutral	Useful	Very useful
Temporary hou...	☐				
Food establish...	☐				
Useful directio...	☐				
Healthcare faci...	☐				
Documents an...	☐				
Legal Situation	☐				
Professional tr...	☐				
Starting Over (...)	☐				
Guardianship o...	☐				
Treatment for ...	☐				
Other former in...	☐				
Benefits, financ...	☐				
Free Legal assi...	☐				
Contact the So...	☐				

Could you please comment on your assessment?

Texto de resposta longa

What other information could the app offer and what improvements would you recommend for the app?

Texto de resposta longa

Thank you very much for your participation. Your comments are very helpful in improving the application!

Descrição (opcional)